

FERRIMAGNETIC GLASS-CERAMICS FOR CANCER THERAPY

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SUMMARY

The aim of this work is characterization of bioactive ferrimagnetic glass-ceramics for magnetic induction hyperthermia. These biomaterials contain different amounts of magnetite crystals, are bioactive and biocompatible to the human bone osteosarcoma cells. The surface of these materials was modified in order to bind two different antitumoral drugs.

Keywords: ferrimagnetic, glass-ceramics, hyperthermia, cancer, drug delivery

INTRODUCTION

Magnetic induction hyperthermia is one of the cancer therapies which uses magnetic materials for the destruction of neoplastic tissue under an alternating magnetic field. Magnetic field is not absorbed by the living tissue and can be applied to deep regions into the body. These magnetic materials can be implanted into the tumour and due to their specific properties, can generate heat under an external alternating magnetic field (usually by hysteresis loss and eddy current loss), destroying the cancer cells [1, 2]. This work is focused on the development of bioactive ferrimagnetic glass-ceramics containing antitumoral drugs for magnetic drug delivery.

Materials and Methods:

Bioactive and biocompatible ferrimagnetic glass-ceramics having the composition in the system $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Na}_2\text{O-CaO-P}_2\text{O}_5\text{-FeO-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ were produced by a traditional melting method. The theoretical percent of magnetite in these samples is 45wt%. A complete characterization was performed in terms of morphology and microstructure: scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), differential thermal analysis (DTA). Magnetic hysteresis cycle was analysed using a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) with a maximum applied field of 12 kOe (956 kA/m), at room temperature, in quasi-static conditions. Calorimetric measurements (specific power loss) were carried out using a magnetic induction furnace, with a magnetic field of 40kA/m and a frequency of 440 kHz. *In vitro* bioactivity was analysed by immersing the samples in a simulated body fluid (SBF) according to Kokubo protocol [3]. After soaking, the samples were analysed by SEM and XRD. Citotoxicity test was carried out by using human bone osteosarcoma cells. All the samples were pre-conditioned in culture

medium for 24h before seeding. The surface of these biomaterials was activated in order to expose hydroxyls groups and to bind two different antitumoral drugs for magnetic drug delivery (doxorubicin and cisplatinium). The efficiency of the surface modification and drug release were investigated by contact angle measurements, UV-spectroscopy, spectrophotometry and X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (XPS).

Results and Discussion:

XRD patterns put in evidence the presence of a unique crystalline phase, magnetite, embedded in an amorphous residual phase. The XRD pattern of a glass-ceramic sample is shown in Figure 1. The reflection peaks were identified as magnetite. The DTA measurements show a glass transition temperature, specific of glass-ceramic materials.

Figure 1 XRD spectra of a glass-ceramic sample (M=magnetite crystals)

SEM micrograph of a glass-ceramic sample after chemical etching (with a solution 1:1 HNO₃:HF, 5% vol. in distilled water) is shown in Figure 2a. As can be seen, small interpenetrated columns formed by octahedral crystals with an average size around 1 μ m are homogeneously distributed in an amorphous matrix. These octahedral crystals are identified as an iron oxide from EDS measurements (Figure 2b).

The room temperature hysteresis loop of a glass-ceramic sample under a magnetic field of 12 kOe is shown in Figure 3. The sample exhibits a magnetic behaviour characteristic of soft magnetic materials. The inset puts in evidence the central part of the hysteresis loop, emphasising the coercive field and the remanence magnetisation. The specific power loss of these glass-ceramics is around 20W/g. The hysteresis loss and the specific power loss are compatible with the temperatures required for hyperthermic treatments of neoplastic tissues.

Figure 2 a) SEM micrograph of a glass-ceramic sample and b) the EDS spectra of the area marked on figure 2a.

Figure 3 Room temperature hysteresis cycle of a glass-ceramic sample

These magnetic glass-ceramics have slow bioactivity kinetics as hydroxylapatite crystals start to precipitate on the materials surface after 2weeks of soaking in a simulated body fluid. Citotoxicity tests show that these glass-ceramic materials are biocompatible to the U2OS osteosarcoma cells. The cells grow healthy and spread in the culture medium containing magnetic glass-ceramics particles (Figure 4).

Figure 4 U2OS osteosarcoma cells after 24 h in culture medium

XPS and contact angle measurements showed that the samples were efficiently functionalised and the two drugs can be covalently linked to the glass-ceramic surface. After one day of uptake at 37°C, 77 ± 7 wt% of doxorubicin and respectively 42 ± 9 wt% of cisplatin are grafted onto the material surface (see Figure 5 a and b). After 1 day of soaking at 37°C, the glass-ceramic powders release around 15 wt% of doxorubicin and about 50 wt% of cisplatin, respectively (see Figure 5 c and d). The release kinetics is not uniform, showing irregular up and down peaks. The maximum amount of drugs released is obtained after 1 day of dipping at 37°C. The drug release kinetics depends on the concentration of the drug absorbed on the biomaterial surface and on the type of solution (water, simulated body fluid).

Figure 5 a) Amounts of doxorubicin (wt%) grafted on samples surface, after one and two uptake days b) amounts of cisplatin (wt%) grafted on samples surface, after one and two uptake days c) amounts of doxorubicin (wt%) released after different times d) amounts of cisplatin (wt%) released after different times

Conclusions:

Ferrimagnetic glass-ceramics were obtained by a traditional melting method. They contain magnetite crystals, homogeneously distributed inside the glass matrix. These biomaterials are both bioactive and biocompatible to human bone osteosarcoma cells. The surface of these materials can be easily modified, in order to bind specific drugs for magnetic drug targeting. Further works concerning the drugs release in simulated body fluid and the study of the drug release kinetics in function of the temperature are in progress.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge P. Tiberto and P. Allia (National Institute of Metrology, Turin, Italy) for the magnetic measurements, Roberto Agu' and Giorgio Manfredi (Manfredi S.p.A, Pinerolo, IT) for the calorimetric measurement facilities, I. Marangi, R. Carbone (European Institute of Oncology, Milan, Italy) for the *in vitro* tests, C. Bianchi and A. Naldoni (Dept. Physical Chemistry and Electrochemistry, Milan University) for XPS measurements and G. Maina (Traumatology Orthopaedics and Occupational Medicine Department, Turin University) for cisplatinum release test. This work was partially funded by the Piedmont Region project, "Functionalized ferrimagnetic materials for solid tumours", 2009.

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